

spraying of fungicide and insecticide were used.

The varieties that yielded high in monoculture also yielded high when intercropped with corn in both seasons (see table). When the varieties were ranked on the basis of yield performance in the tests, among the five top yielders in monoculture in the dry season were EG-MG-174-3, CES 55, S8 (Green), M350, and CES-1T-2. When intercropped with corn, the top yielders were CES 55, EG-MG-174-3, CES-1T-2, CES-U-1, and

S8 (Green). The test varieties performed differently in the wet season. The five top yielders for monoculture were CES-1T-2, M350, MG-50-10A (Y), CES-1D-21, and EG-MG-174-3. In intercropping, the top yielders were CES-1T-2, CES-1D-21, CES-1F-5, M350, and MG-50-10A (Y).

In the dry season, correlations of mung bean yields and rank orders for monocrops vs corn association gave positive and significant r values ($r=0.75^*$ for yield, and $r=0.80^{**}$ for rank order). Varieties also exhibited similar

relationships in the wet-season planting ($r=0.74^*$ for yield, and $r=0.88^{**}$ for rank order). Correlations of mung bean yields and rank orders for monocrops vs intercrops over two seasons were also found significant at the 1% level of significance ($r=0.88^{**}$ for yield, and $r=0.82^{**}$ for rank order). Although seasons influence the yield and cultivar ranking, promising mung bean varieties can be screened in monoculture and recommendations for other associated systems can be made. ■

Reducing turnaround time and cost of production by zero and minimum tillage in intensive rice cropping systems

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A longer turnaround time has been one of the most important constraints to intensive rice cropping patterns, particularly those involving modern rice varieties, in Bangladesh. Farmers usually keep a turnaround time of 2–3 weeks between rice crops. The later part of the period is often used for land preparation. Four tillage treatments were used in an experiment undertaken in 1979 aus in a farmer's field at the BRRI Cropping Systems Research site at Salna to

determine the effect of zero and minimum tillage and reduced turnaround time on the yield of aus (Chandina) rice following a crop of boro (Pajam) rice. Both crops were irrigated. In the experimental aus crop, the farmer applied fertilizer at 56 kg N/ha, 28 kg P_2O_5 /ha, and 28 kg K_2O /ha. Forty-eight percent of the nitrogen and all P_2O_5 and K_2O were applied basally; the rest of the nitrogen was applied in two topdressings. The treatments were replicated twice and received uniform water management, weeding, pest control, and other operations.

A 1-day turnaround period was needed for the zero tillage treatment; a 4-day period for the minimum tillage treatment. High-intensity tillage was

applied within 3-day turnaround time. The farmer plowed 7 times and laddered 4 times during a 15-day turnaround period. There was no significant difference in grain yield due to tillage practice.

However, land preparation for minimum tillage cost \$14.02/ha; that for high-intensity tillage within 3 days, \$60.93/ha; and that for the farmer's level of tillage, \$71.61/ha. The zero tillage practice in the irrigated rice paddies reduced the turnaround time to 1 day without reducing grain yields, thus enabling the farmers to grow more intensive cropping patterns. Expensive land preparation could be totally avoided in the irrigated areas by adopting the zero-tillage technique. ■

Machinery development and testing

Power and cost requirements for field operations in rice cultivation

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The human and animal power requirements for various field operations were monitored during cultivation of the 1979 aus rice crop at the BRRI cropping systems research site, Salna, Dacca district. Detailed records were maintained on the actual human- and animal-hour requirements by using a

stopwatch for the various operations of 12 farmers who grew aus rice (4 used traditional varieties, 8 grew modern ones). The costs of human and paired-animal-hours were computed at the rate of \$0.08 and \$0.17/hour, respectively.

The table shows that 969 human-hours/ha costing \$80.87/ha, and 167 paired-animal-hours/ha costing \$27.87/ha were used for all field operations. Weeding accounted for the highest human-hours (37%), followed by transplanting (19%), harvesting (18%), and plowing (15%). Animal power was used only in plowing (89%) and laddering (11%).

When modern varieties were used, the total human- and paired-animal-hours per hectare were 822 and 254, at a corresponding total cost of \$68.47 and \$42.40. Plowing required the maximum human-hours (29%), followed by harvesting, weeding, and transplanting. Plowing also used 93% animal power. Interestingly, the total per-hectare power costs for the traditional and modern varieties were almost the same. The study showed that plowing, transplanting, weeding, and harvesting were the major field operations requiring 89% of the total power requirements of both traditional and modern varieties. ■

Average human-hours, animal-hours, and costs required for various field operations in the cultivation of traditional and modern varieties of aus rice. 1979 aus season, Saina village, Dacca district, Bangladesh.^a

Operation	Traditional variety (4 samples)				Modern variety (8 samples)			
	Human-h/ha	Cost of human power (\$/ha)	Paired-animal-h/ha	Cost of animal power (\$/ha)	Human-h/ha	Cost of human power (\$/ha)	Paired-animal-h/ha	Cost of animal power (\$/ha)
Plowing	149 (15)	12.40	149 (89)	24.87	237 (29)	19.73	237 (93)	39.53
Laddering	18 (2)	1.53	18 (11)	3.00	17 (2)	1.40	17 (7)	2.87
Trimming levees	43 (5)	3.60	—	—	12 (1)	1.00	—	—
Applying fertilizer	10 (1)	0.87	—	—	7 (1)	0.60	—	—
Applying manure	00	0.00	—	—	18 (2)	1.53	—	—
Uprooting seedlings	24 (3)	2.00	—	—	13 (2)	1.07	—	—
Transplanting	186 (19)	15.53	—	—	131 (16)	10.93	—	—
Weeding	361 (37)	30.07	—	—	161 (20)	13.40	—	—
Applying pesticide	00	0.00	—	—	29 (3)	2.40	—	—
Harvesting	178 (18)	14.27	—	—	197 (24)	16.40	—	—
Total	969	80.87	167	27.87	822	68.45	254	42.40

^aNumbers in parentheses indicate the percentage of total for the column.

Announcements

IRRI will provide illustrations for translations of *A farmer's primer on growing rice*

Recommendations given to farmers in the past have often failed to answer questions such as why a farmer incubates seed, why he applies fertilizer, or how and when fertilizer should be incorporated. *A farmer's primer on growing rice* was designed to help the progressive farmer or rice specialist understand and explain *why* and *how* the improved rice varieties and technology increase production.

Several national rice improvement programs have requested IRRI's cooperation in the translation and local printing of *A farmer's primer*.

Therefore, IRRI will provide black-and-white prints of all illustrations and artwork in the book (with English text blocked out) to rice agencies interested in

publishing local-language editions. The cost is US\$16 (actual reproduction cost plus airmail postage and 1 English edition).

Dr. Benito S. Vergara, IRRI plant physiologist, authored the 221-page handbook during a sabbatic leave at the Southeast Asian Regional Center for Graduate Study and Research in Agriculture (SEARCA), Los Baños, Philippines.

Individuals or organizations in developing nations may purchase *A farmer's primer* at US\$2.20/copy (postpaid, surface mail) or at \$4.30/copy (postpaid, air mail) (P15.10 or P25.50 in the Philippines). Those in highly developed nations may order the book at \$5.20/copy (surface mail) or \$7.30 (air mail).

Interested organizations may write to: Office of Information Services (OIS), IRRI, P.O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines. ■